

Effect of clamping force and environmental conditioning on the mechanical performance of bolted composite laminates

S. Spyridonidis¹, T. Laux¹, B.C. Kim¹, S. Ashworth², and **N. Chandarana**^{1,*}

¹Bristol Composites Institute, University of Bristol, Bristol, UK

²BAE Systems

[*neha.chandarana@bristol.ac.uk](mailto:neha.chandarana@bristol.ac.uk)

bristol.ac.uk

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Presentation outline

- Bolted composite joints in aerospace
- Specimen design, test matrix, and experimental set-up
- Finite element analysis
- Experimental and numerical results
- Conclusions and future work

Bolted composite joints in aerospace

Wide spectrum of operating conditions

High temperatures

[1]

- 120°C for a supersonic flight
- 60°C, stationary at the runway

High humidity

[2]

- 85%RH, Southeast Asia

Torque up level

[3]

1. Prisco, J. (2023, July 22). Why high temperatures can make planes too heavy to take off. CNN. <https://edition.cnn.com/travel/article/climate-change-airplane-takeoff-scn/index.html>
2. Associated, A., & Place, T. (2020, January 9). Qantas plane slides off the end of runway into mud at Newman Airport after a tropical cyclone in WA. Mail Online. <https://www.dailymail.co.uk/news/article-7867541/Qantas-plane-slides-end-runway-mud-Newman-Airport-tropical-cyclone-WA.html>
3. In-Pavement Light Fixture Bolts (added 12/27/2018). (2018, December 26). Federal Aviation Administration. Retrieved August 19, 2023, from https://www.faa.gov/airports/engineering/engineering_briefs

Bolted composite joints in aerospace

Aim:

Investigation of the effect of fastener torque, high humidity, and elevated temperature on the mechanical strength and failure modes of bolted composite joints

Novelty:

The identification of the correlation between the filled hole strength, environmental parameters (humidity, temperature), and the applied clamping force

Specimen design and text matrix

Specimen geometry

Filled hole specimens

Specimen type	Testing temperature	Humidity level	Number of specimens x torque level
F1	Ambient (25°C)	Ambient (not conditioned)	5 x low (1 Nm) 5 x high (15.4 Nm)
F2	Ambient (25°C)	High (85°C at 85%RH)	3 x low (1 Nm) 3 x high (15.4 Nm)
F3	Elevated (120°C)	High (85°C at 85%RH)	5 x low (1 Nm) 4 x intermediate (7.7 Nm) 5 x high (15.4 Nm)

Open hole specimens

Specimen type	Testing temperature	Humidity level	Number of specimens
O1	Ambient (25°C)	Ambient (not conditioned)	3
O2	Elevated (120°C)	High (85°C at 85%RH)	3

Experimental set-up

Room temperature

Elevated temperature (120°C)

Bespoke thermal chamber

Finite element analysis

- Mesoscale model with solid elements (C3D8R)
- Damage initiation criterion (LaRC05)
- IM7/8552 properties at:
 - Ambient temperature and humidity
 - Elevated temperature and high humidity

Experimental results

RTD: Room/ambient temperature, dry - **RTW:** Room/ambient temperature, wet - **ETW:** Elevated temperature, wet

Comparison of FEA and experimental data

Open hole RTD

Strain ϵ_{11} , for lines through width RTD Open Hole Specimen

Open hole ETW

Strain ϵ_{11} , for lines through width ETW Open Hole Specimen

Filled hole high torque RTD

Strain ϵ_{11} , for lines through width RTD High Torqued Specimen

Ply-by-ply failure indices - RTD

Load: 34.9 kN

Dry specimens tested at room temperature

0° Ply

Open Hole

Low

High

90° Ply

Open Hole

Low

High

UVARM1: Matrix cracking failure index - UVARM4: Fibre fracture failure index

Ply-by-ply failure indices - ETW

Load: 30.3kN

High humidity (wet) specimens tested at elevated temperature

0° Ply

90° Ply

Open Hole Low Intermediate High

Open Hole Low Intermediate High

UVARM1: Matrix cracking failure index - **UVARM4:** Fibre fracture failure index

Conclusions and next steps

- The moisture content at room temperatures does not affect the strength or the stiffness of filled hole specimens
- The presence of the bolt and the clamping force act beneficially for strength in room temperature conditions
- At elevated temperature, the strength of low-torqued and open-hole specimens is increased compared to room temperature, while a higher clamping force causes a reduction in strength
- High clamping forces delay fibre failure initiation but promote matrix failure

Future work

- Experimental: Measuring the clamp-up and the clamp-up relaxation by instrumenting the bolt; evaluate damage under the washer area using X-ray CT
- Numerical: Analyse filled hole test using a progressive damage strategy; include delamination damage in the model

Thank you for your attention!
Any questions?

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S. Spyridonidis¹, T. Laux¹, B.C. Kim¹, S. Ashworth², and
N. Chandarana^{1,*}

[*neha.chandarana@bristol.ac.uk](mailto:neha.chandarana@bristol.ac.uk)

bristol.ac.uk

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Combined *in-situ* microscopy and
acoustic emission monitoring of
transverse cracking in CFRP cross-ply
laminates

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S. Spyridonidis^{1,2}, G. Allegri¹, T. Laux¹, and N. Chandarana¹

¹Bristol Composites Institute, University of Bristol, Bristol, UK
²spyros.spyridonidis@bristol.ac.uk

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